

Oral Presentation #63 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

AUTHORS

Elif Negis
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4070-3558>

Yasemin Kilic Ozturk
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1463-6627>

AFFILIATIONS

Izmir Kiraz No. 1 Family Health Center
Izmir, Turkey

University of Health Sciences,
Tepecik Training and Research Hospital
Department of Family Medicine
Izmir, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Recent developments in medical technology, particularly in diagnostics and treatment, have prolonged life expectancy in chronic diseases and increased the demand for personalized care. Palliative care improves quality of life by relieving pain and addressing physical, psychosocial, and spiritual problems through early diagnosis and holistic evaluation (Fallon & Hanks, 2013; World Health Organization, n.d.). This study aimed to evaluate the quality of life and associated factors in individuals receiving early palliative care in a family medicine-led center (Figure 1).

Materials and Methods: This prospective cohort study was conducted at the Palliative Care Unit of Izmir University of Health Sciences Tepecik Training and Research Hospital between October 15, 2019, and March 15, 2020. Inclusion criteria were age over 18, cognitive competence, and consent to participate. A total of 142 inpatients were evaluated at admission and again 6 months later. Data collection involved three stages: baseline demographic and clinical data, the 36-Item Short Form Survey (SF-36) administered face-to-face, and a follow-up interview at 6 months including quality of life reassessment and post-discharge healthcare use. The study was completed with 91 participants.

Results: The mean age was 64.48 ± 10.8 years; 76.8% were male. The most common admission reasons were fatigue (88.7%) and pain (52.8%). A cancer diagnosis was present in 92.2% of patients. The average illness duration was 17.54 ± 25.50 months. At 6 months, 38.5% had one emergency/hospital visit, 5.5% had multiple visits, and 56% had none. SF-36 subscale scores increased in all domains at follow-up. Patients with post-discharge hospital/emergency admissions had lower physical and emotional role scores. The energy subscale improved significantly in patients with illness durations ≥ 12 months. A positive correlation was found between illness duration and energy and pain subscales (Haun et al., 2017). No significant relationship was observed between time from diagnosis to palliative care and survival.

Conclusion: In the study there was a significant positive correlation between the time from diagnosis to palliative care application and the quality of life in the energy and pain subdimensions, no significant correlation was found between the time from diagnosis to palliative care application and survival. Although there is no consensus on the timing of palliative care (Şenel & Koçak, 2020), patients should be informed early about their right to access this service.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Palliative care, quality of life, home care, biopsychosocial approach

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Fallon, M., & Hanks, G. (2013). *ABC of palliative care* (pp. 1–3). John Wiley & Sons.

Haun, M. W., Estel, S., Rücker, G., Friederich, H. C., Villalobos, M., Thomas, M., & Hartmann, M. (2017). Early palliative care for adults with advanced cancer.

Şenel, G., & Koçak, N. (2020). Palyatif bakım kalite standartları. *Türkiye Klinikleri Medical Oncology - Special Topics*, 13(1), 5–10.

World Health Organization. (n.d.). *Palliative care*. <https://www.who.int/cancer/palliative/definition/en/>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Elif Negis

Izmir Kiraz No. 1 Family Health Center

Izmir, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4070-3558>

elifnegiss@gmail.com